

MULTI-COUNTRY ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTS OF HEAT ON PREGNANCY AND PERINATAL OUTCOMES

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition/Description
APGAR	Appearance, Pulse, Grimace, Activity and Respiration (Newborn health assessment scoring system at 5 minutes)
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CDS	Climate Data Store
CEDAP	Certificate of Delivery Care Registry (Italy)
CEpiP	Centre for Perinatal Epidemiology (Brussels & Wallonia)
CI	Confidence Interval
DLNM	Distributed Lag Non-Linear Model
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
ELSTAT	Hellenic Statistical Authority
ERA5	The 5th European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts Reanalysis Product
HDSS	Health and Demographic Surveillance System
HR	Hazard ratio
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
DEP-Lazio	Department of Epidemiology of the Lazio Region Health Service, ASL Roma 1 (Italy)
KI	Karolinska Institutet (Sweden)
LBW	Low birth weight
LGA	Large for gestational age
MNCH	Maternal, Neonatal, and Child Health
NDVI	Normalised Difference Vegetation Index
NUTS-3	Third level of European Union's regional statistical classification
OR	Odds ratio
PTB	Preterm birth
REDCap	Research Electronic Data Capture
SB	Stillbirth
SGA	Small for gestational age
SPE	Study Centre for Perinatal Epidemiology (Flanders)
UGRAZ	Graz University
UK	United Kingdom
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
UTCI	Universal Thermal Climate Index (a thermal comfort index)
UTH	University of Thessaly (Greece)
VIDA	Vaccines and Infectious Diseases Analytics (University of Witwatersrand)
WBGT	Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (a heat stress index)
WP	Work Package
Wits RHI	Research institute of the University of the Witwatersrand (South Africa)

Executive summary

This report describes the investigation of the effects of heat on pregnancy and perinatal outcomes through a first-time multi-country analysis approach. Therefore, we included countries from Europe, Africa, Latin America, and the Caribbean which provided perinatal health data, alongside socio-economic characteristics, ranging from individual hospitals to nationwide coverage. In combination with environmental data, statistical methods such as case-crossover and time-to-event studies were used to quantify relationships between heat exposures and perinatal health outcomes. The first round of data analysis, which is the subject of this report, examined birth outcomes such as preterm birth and stillbirth. The cross-country analysis shows an association with heat exposure, particularly in the third trimester and last week of pregnancy. During the latter period, we observe that African countries in particular demonstrate a stronger association, which is likely due to higher baseline risks and less ability to adapt to heat in lower resource settings. The second round of data analysis will focus on maternal complications, such as hypertension and gestational diabetes, to better characterise the biological mechanisms and identify the periods of pregnancy when women are most vulnerable. Additionally, these results will be synthesised to inform the selection of global heat-health indicators, a topic that will be discussed in the upcoming joint WHO-UNICEF-UNFPA-WMO publication. In light of ongoing global warming, our findings highlight the need for further research, as there is an urgent need to develop better protection for mothers and babies at risk of heat exposure.

1 Introduction

This report presents the findings from country-level analyses conducted by HIGH Horizons to deepen understanding of the relationship between short-term and long-term heat exposure and various perinatal health outcomes. The study spans countries across Europe, Africa, Latin America, and the Caribbean, using heat metrics such as daily mean temperature, Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT), Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI), and the Heat Index. A first report with the initial findings was published in 2023, and is completed with the update in this report.

➤ 2023 report

The initial heat-health analysis focused on the countries involved in the HIGH Horizons project: Greece, Italy, Sweden, Kenya, and South Africa and examined one maternal and newborn health (MNH) outcome: preterm birth [1]. Key findings include:

- No significant difference across the studied countries in overall risk of preterm birth due to heat exposure;
- Variation in the temperature threshold at which heat exposure increases the risk of preterm birth;
- Minimal differences between the various heat metrics and their association with preterm birth incidence.

This initial analysis was complemented by a pooled time-series study on the impact of ambient heat on all-cause mortality in children under five in Africa. Data were sourced from the INDEPTH network and the Health and Demographic Surveillance System. Findings revealed that the effect of extreme heat on mortality risk in children younger than 5 years varies by age group, region, and season [2].

➤ 2025 report

For this report update we made some methodological enhancements. To address challenges such as heterogeneity in exposure assessment, outcome definitions, confounding factors, and statistical methods – common in prior studies – we implemented a standardised data protocol [3], harmonised statistical approaches, and unified analysis scripts across all countries.

The geographical scope was expanded to include additional countries in Europe, Africa, Latin America, and the Caribbean. MNH outcomes were listed and prioritised based on a systematic literature review on the effects of heat exposure on maternal, foetal, and neonatal health [4], also carried out by the HIGH Horizons team.

2 Background

Several meta-analyses have revealed that higher ambient temperatures are associated with increased risks of preterm birth (PTB), stillbirth (SB), and low birth weight [4,5]. A global study involving 14 lower-middle income countries also showed that extreme heat increased the risks of PTB and SB [6]. In addition, some studies investigated trimester-specific exposures. For example, a national birth cohort from mainland China mentioned pregnant women in their first and second trimesters are more susceptible to high temperatures [7]. However, another study found that exposed to heat is associated with risk of PTB during the third trimester and foetal heart rate may mediate the association [8]. The findings in exploring the susceptible window during pregnancy are inconsistent. Wang et al. reported that increased demands for oxygen and nutrients by foetus in the late pregnancy might enhance their vulnerability to environmental risk factors [9].

Animal studies further explored the potential mechanisms underlying the associations:

- 1) heat stress reduces blood flow to the uterus and placenta, which caused abnormal placenta growth [10];
- 2) heat stress impairs transportation of essential amino acid and glucose to foetus [11];
- 3) heat stress activates hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal stress-response axis, increased cortisol exposure is linked to low birth weight [12];
- 4) heat stress triggers the release of placenta hormones and immune makers [12].

Most studies use mean temperature as a measure of heat exposure to explore maternal and foetal health. However, temperature as one of heat indicators may not completely capture the combined influence of wind stress, solar radiation, and humidity on health outcomes [13]. To improve this limitation, a few studies also apply UTCI and WBGT as heat indicators to investigate the associations with adverse birth outcomes [14,15].

So far most studies have focused on short-term effects of ambient temperature on adverse birth outcomes, such as a few days before delivery. However, it is worth noting that pregnant women are exposed to ambient temperatures for a much longer period, as it takes around nine months from conception to delivery. Therefore, evaluating the effect of long-term ambient temperature on outcomes of pregnancy is also important. We therefore split our data analyses into one on short-term (<7 days) and one on long-term (whole pregnancy) heat exposure and its relation to perinatal health outcomes.

3 Data

Data required for the heat-health analyses can be grouped as: health data, environmental data, and contextual data. The sources and datasets used for the short and long-term analyses are detailed in a separate deliverable 'D2.2 Environmental and health database 2' [16]. In this chapter we describe the key variables, including heat metrics and perinatal health outcomes.

3.1 Environmental data

Heat exposure is assessed using heat metrics, alongside ambient air temperature. Heat metrics were chosen based on a previous study by Ioannou et al., (2022) which showed that WBGT and UTCI outperformed other indices across a range of physiological tests such as heart rate and metabolic rate [17]. The HIGH Horizons scoping review of heat metrics used in perinatal and maternal health studies showed that alongside WBGT and UTCI, heat index and apparent temperature have previously been used by studies [18].

3.2 Perinatal health data

3.2.1 Priority health outcomes

We prioritised perinatal health outcomes based on their availability across all countries.

Our *short-term* heat exposure analysis includes singleton births, and assesses three adverse birth outcomes:

- (1) preterm birth, defined as the delivery of an infant before 37 weeks' gestation;
- (2) stillbirth, defined as foetal death prior to the complete expulsion of the foetus;
- (3) low APGAR score, defined as an APGAR score <7 at five minutes post birth.

Gestational age is determined using the best estimate available (second trimester ultrasound or last menstrual period if ultrasound was unavailable).

The adverse birth outcomes investigated in the *long-term* heat exposure analysis include:

- (1) preterm birth;
- (2) stillbirth;
- (3) small for gestational age, being a newborn who weighs less than 90% of newborns of the same gestational age at birth (below the 10th percentile);
- (4) large for gestational age, being a newborn who weighs more than 90% of newborns of the same gestational age at birth (above the 90th percentile).

The data of the countries and regions listed below will be analysed.

3.2.2 Belgium

For this study, data were sourced from the Belgian Birth Register, which records all live births (irrespective of gestational age or birth weight) as well as stillbirths occurring from 22 weeks of gestation or 500 grams onwards. Data collection is regionally organised: records from Brussels and Wallonia are maintained by the Centre for Perinatal Epidemiology (CEpiP), while those from Flanders are managed by the Study Centre for Perinatal Epidemiology (SPE). These regional datasets were combined for the purpose of analysis.

The dataset covers births from 1 January 2012 to 31 December 2022 and includes 1,285,495 singleton births across Belgium. Information is available for both newborns and their mothers. Of the newborns, 51.2% were male and 48.8% female. A majority of mothers were aged between 25 and 34 years (62.8%), and 40.3% had attained a university-level or higher education. Conceptions and births were evenly distributed across all seasons.

Among 1,240,231 singleton live births considered for analysis, 6.6% (81,735) were preterm, 0.4% (4,675) were stillbirths, 5.4% (66,481) had low birth weight, 6.8% (84,098) were categorised as small for gestational age (SGA), and 13.8% (170,855)

as large for gestational age (LGA).

Figure 1 shows the annual number of births in Belgium from 2012 to 2022. A gradual decline can be observed from 2012 to 2020. A slight uptick in births was observed in 2021, but the number decreased again in 2022.

Figure 1. Distribution of births per year in Belgium

3.2.3 Greece

The national dataset from Greece includes 2 316 655 births between 1999 to 2021. Available variables for each birth include i) live or stillbirth, ii) cause of stillbirth, iii) person present at birth, iv) gestational age at birth, v) birth weight (grams), vi) maternal age, vii) mode of delivery (vaginal birth, caesarean section, instrumental delivery), viii) maternal nationality, ix) marital status, x) residence (urban/rural/semi urban), and xi) number of newborns. The date of birth (DD/MM/YY) and the municipality of residence of the mother is available for all births. Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT) is the owner of the data. In this dataset, preterm delivery (<37 weeks' gestation) occurred in 9.1% of cases, with most being moderately preterm (8.1%), and smaller proportions very preterm (0.8%) or extremely preterm (0.3%). Low birth weight (<2500 g) was observed in 8.5% of infants, again predominantly in the moderate category (7.5%), with very

low (0.7%) and extremely low (0.3%) birth weight much less frequent. Stillbirths were rare, accounting for 0.4% of total births.

Figure 2 shows the annual number of births from 1999 to 2021. Birth counts rose steadily from around 100,000 in 1999 to a peak of approximately 120,000 in 2008–2009. This was followed by a marked decline after 2010, coinciding with the economic crisis period, reaching lows near 85,000–90,000 in the late 2010s. The overall trend reflects a long-term reduction in births over the past two decades despite short-term fluctuations.

Figure 2. Distribution of births per year in Greece

3.2.4 Italy

The data source is the Certificate of Delivery Care Registry (CEDAP) of the Lazio Region (a regional database) [19]. The dataset includes all births recorded between 2001 and 2019, totalling approximately 858,000 births from women with geocoded residential addresses in the region (about 40,000 births per year) (Figure 3). Most deliveries occurred in the province of Rome (76.7%), with 52.9% of the total taking place in the metropolitan area. Births were evenly distributed across the seasons.

Figure 3. Distribution of births per year in the Lazio Region, Italy

The dataset contains detailed information on both infant (e.g., date and hospital of birth, singleton or twin pregnancy, sex, gestational age, birth weight) and maternal characteristics (e.g., age, parity, education level, employment status, origin, and geocoded residence). Most newborns were male (51.5%), and most mothers were aged 25–34 years (57%) and had completed high school degree (45.7%).

For our analyses, we included only singleton births ($n = 829,242$), comprising 1,255 stillbirths (0.2%) and 827,987 live births (99.8%). Of the live births, 50,244 (6.0%) were born preterm (<37 gestational weeks). Additional outcomes were identified, including low APGAR score (validated for all years except 2008, 2009, and 2010, resulting in 4,022 cases). In total, 44,772 (5.4%) newborns were classified as having low birth weight (LBW), 105,752 (12.8%) as large for gestational age, and 60,991 (7.4%) as small for gestational age. Information on delivery type was also available: 327,312 deliveries were performed via caesarean section, of which 149,360 were emergency procedures.

3.2.5 Sweden

The current register for the analyses encompasses the period starting 1st January 2014 until 31st December 2019. The dataset contains information on both infants and mothers with geocoded residential addresses. In total, there were 558,638 births from 2014 to 2019, with approximately 90,000 births per year (Figure 4). 51.5% participants were male newborns and 48.5% were female newborns. Most mothers were aged 25-34 years (65.9%) and most of them had higher educational level (bachelor's degree or higher, 43.6%). The timing of conception and birth were equally distributed throughout the four seasons.

Among 93,985 caesarean section deliveries, 54,244 (57.7%) were emergency caesarean sections.

Among the singleton births, 27,865 (5.0%) were born preterm, 1,874 (0.3%) were stillborn, 18,583 (3.3%) were LBW, 51,247 (9.2%) were classified as SGA, and 58,785 (10.5%) were classified as LGA. In addition, 7,588 cases had low (<7) 5-min APGAR score.

Figure 4. Distribution of births per year in Sweden

3.2.6 Kenya

The data used are from 2017 to 2022 for Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa. This is a local scale dataset. Data are retrieved using the Aga Khan Hospital Surveillance Dashboard. It provides birth records between 2017 and July 2023, with an average of 520 births in the hospital per year (Figure 5). Information on type of delivery, stillbirths, APGAR scores and live preterm births is included. The maternal age group is the only contextual variable provided within the dataset. The seasonal trend indicates that most preterm births take place in at the beginning of the hottest period and towards the end of a short rainy season in Kenya. However, the small number of preterm births limits our ability to interpret the data.

Figure 5. Distribution of births per year in Aga Khan Hospital Mombasa, Kenya

Note: For 2023, only births through July were recorded.

3.2.7 South Africa

The data used in HIGH Horizons is provided by the Vaccines and Infectious Diseases Analytics Research Unit of the University of the Witwatersrand (Wits VIDA). Wits VIDA funds and maintains a passive surveillance (birth register) dataset for the Soweto region of South Africa. Information is recorded on all deliveries at midwife-led clinics and a tertiary referral hospital in the region (N = 10). In total,

189,669 singleton births between March 2016 - March 2022 were included in analyses (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Distribution of births per year in Soweto, South Africa

Of these births, 92,207 (48.6%) were female and 94,958 (50.1%) were male (2,504 were of unknown sex). Most of the women were aged 25-35 (n=94,953, 50.1%). For the short term heat exposure analysis, from a total of 189,669 singleton live births, 18,280 (17.1%¹) were born preterm, 2,394 (1.3%) were stillborn, and 8,575 (4.5%) cases had low (<7) 5-min APGAR score.

3.2.8 Sub-Saharan African region

Data from the sub-Saharan African region included 138,015 singleton births from a prospective observational study in 16 hospitals in Benin, Malawi, Tanzania and Uganda, which were collected as part of the Action Leveraging Evidence to Reduce perinatal mortality and morbidity (ALERT) study [20].

In each of the countries, four medium-size hospitals were included with more than 2,500 births per annum. Hospitals were typically district or regional public and

¹ PTB in the Soweto cohort was restricted to births in the tertiary facility only (N=106,626) as the gestational age at the clinic were not reliable.

private-non-profit (faith-based) facilities, although the national referral hospital in Cotonou, Benin, also took part in the study.

Within the HIGH Horizons study, we included all mother–baby pairs admitted for childbirth in any of the hospitals between 1 July 2021 and 31 December 2023 [21]. We excluded mother–baby pairs who were referred to the hospitals after giving birth. Protocol details are published elsewhere [22].

3.2.9 Latin America and Caribbean region

In the Region of the Americas, the Women’s, Maternal, Neonatal and Reproductive Health (WH) Unit, from the Department of Health Systems and Services (HSS) at the Pan American Health Organization (PAHO); coordinates a network of sentinel centres for maternal-perinatal health surveillance across institutions from the region. All the institutions use SIP-PLUS as a common data collection system. The SIP-PLUS database contains the data from the electronic perinatal medical records. The dataset contains information on both newborns and women. The perinatal medical record registers individual data and health outcomes from the clinical follow-up during pregnancy, from the date of the first prenatal visit to the maternal and newborn discharge. It records personal and family history information, obstetric history, information of the current pregnancy, of each antenatal care visit, information from labour and birth, neonatal and maternal outcomes, presence of maternal morbidity and information on maternal and child discharge.

We excluded multiple births and records lacking information on the facility where delivery occurred. An imputation process was applied to handle missing values for maternal age. When imputation was not possible, the corresponding records were excluded from the dataset.

The dataset includes 201,636 singleton births recorded across 15 hospitals between February 2008 and December 2024. Data were collected from seven countries in Latin America: Honduras contributed 35.3% (71,080) of the records,

followed by the Dominican Republic with 20.8% (41,013), Argentina with 17.7% (34,510), Guatemala with 8.4% (16,891), Bolivia with 8.1% (16,306), Uruguay with 6.3% (12,669), and Ecuador with 4.1% (8,167). Among the newborns, 50.7% (102,367) were male, and 1.5% (3,027) had missing information on sex. Preterm births accounted for 7.3% (14,877) of cases, 9.2% (18,458) had low birth weight, and 4.6% (8,865) were classified as 'small for gestational age'. Stillbirths represented 0.6% (1,232) of births, and 1.5% (2,972) of newborns had an APGAR score below 7 at five minutes.

In terms of maternal characteristics, 62.0% (125,073) of women were of mixed race, and 7.9% (15,966) identified as Black. More than half of the women (51.7%, 104,296) were younger than 25 years, and 37.5% (76,515) had completed primary education. Most women (88.1%, 168,113) reported living with a partner.

3.3 Contextual data

We listed all potential covariates according to the literature, and took them into account in the long-term heat exposure analysis:

- Municipality code
- Season of conception (Winter, Spring, Autumn, Summer), year of birth
- Infant sex (male, female) (not available in Greece)
- Maternal characteristics:
 - maternal age in years (≤ 24 , 25–34, ≥ 35)
 - body mass index (BMI categories of the mother at first antenatal care visit: [underweight (< 18.5 kg/m²), normal (18.5–24.9 kg/m²), overweight (25.0–29.9 kg/m²), obese (≥ 30.0 kg/m²)] (not available in Italy)
 - maternal educational level (Primary or lower; High school; bachelor's degree or higher).

4 Methods

Using several heat stress metrics, statistical approaches such as case-crossover and time-to-event analyses were employed to quantify the short-term respectively long-term impact of heat exposure on perinatal health outcomes.

4.1 Heat exposure assessment

We selected daily mean 2 meter air temperature as our main exposure index given its interpretability and availability across the regions. In addition, we examined alternative indices to capture heat stress, including WBGT, UTCI and heat index (Table 1).

Table 1. Description of heat metrics

Heat Index	Source	Description
2m Air Temperature	Copernicus Climate Change Service Climate Data Store: ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present [23]	ERA5 hourly data on single atmospheric levels from 1940 to present. This dataset provides air temperature at 2 meters above ground level with good spatial (0.25°) and temporal (hourly) resolution.
Wet Bulb Globe Temperature	Zenodo: WBGT Daily Maximum, Mean, Minimum 1979-2021 (Brimicombe WBGT method, from hourly ERA5 data) [24]	WBGT Daily Maximum, Mean, Minimum data spanning 1979–2021, calculated using the Brimicombe WBGT method based on hourly ERA5 reanalysis data. WBGT combines temperature, humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation effects, widely used for assessing heat stress in occupational and sports settings.
Universal Thermal Climate Index	Copernicus Climate Change Service Climate Data Store: Thermal comfort indices derived from ERA5 reanalysis [25]	Thermal comfort indices derived from ERA5 reanalysis data, providing a measure of perceived outdoor thermal stress accounting for temperature, wind, humidity, and radiation. UTCI is used in climate impact assessments and human biometeorology.

Heat Index	Source	Description
Heat Index	ECMWF data provided to the project through a data sharing agreement with UGRAZ	A composite index combining air temperature and relative humidity to quantify the human-perceived equivalent temperature, reflecting how hot it feels. Frequently used in heat warning systems and public health advisories.

We obtained hourly air temperature and UTCI from the ERA5 reanalysis dataset, available at the 0.25x0.25km grid scale at the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) through the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS) [26]. WBGT was processed using the python Thermofeel library, and Heat Index was obtained directly from ECMWF.

We aggregated all hourly heat exposures to daily minimum, mean, maximum and diurnal variation (daily maximum minus daily minimum). We evaluated exposures across multiple lag periods, up to six days prior to birth. Exposures were assigned to the births based on the finest spatial resolution available: mother's residential address (Italy, Sweden), hospital of birth (Benin, Malawi, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda), or downscaled to the municipality of mother's residence (Greece) [27].

4.2 Case-crossover study

4.2.1 Statistical modelling

We followed a two-step approach. First, we estimated country-specific associations between heat and birth outcomes employing a time-stratified case-crossover study design, to capture short-term effects (i.e. a week before birth) [28]. We employed a distributed lag non-linear model (DLNM), which accounts for both the non-linear exposure-response relationship and the delayed effects of exposure over time [29]. We used mean air temperature with a lag of 6 days for our main analyses as previous studies have demonstrated increased effect sizes for longer lags [4]. For the exposure response relationship, we selected a natural cubic B-spline with three knots placed at the 10th, 75th and 90th percentiles of

location-specific yearly temperature. This placement was guided by previous literature on temperature-related health effects, particularly in relation to heat [4]. For the lag response relationship, we selected a natural cubic B-spline with two internal knots placed at equal intervals on the log scale. We fit conditional logistic regression models to estimate the odds ratio (OR) and 95% confidence interval of an adverse birth outcome comparing the 99th versus the 75th location-specific temperature percentile. The stillbirth results for Benin, Malawi, Tanzania and Uganda were published previously [30].

In the second step, we performed random-effect meta-analyses to pool the estimates of the country-specific associations. Where appropriate, we present random-effect meta-analyses and meta-regression results of all country estimates. Appropriateness was based on the difference between common and fixed effects meta-analysis models and observed heterogeneity of results (I^2 and number of countries with harmful and protective effects).

To validate the robustness of our estimates, we performed multiple sensitivity analyses. First, to validate our initial model, we altered the parameterisation of the DLNMs (polynomials and splines, knot points). Second, we explored different lag patterns (0-6 days) and centring points (Table 2).

Table 2. Parameters for sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity Analysis	Default Parameter	Moderations
DLNM Smoothing function Function for arglag and argvar in crossbasis function	Natural cubic B-spline with 2 knots	Polynomial function <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 degrees • 3 degrees Cubic B-Spline, with varying number of knots <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 knots • 4 knots • 5 knots
Lags Number of days of lagged exposure	0-6 days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0 days • 0-1 days • 0-2 days • 0-3 days • 0-4 days • 0-5 days

Sensitivity Analysis	Default Parameter	Moderations
Knot points for smoothing function for predictor Knot points when predictor smoothing function is Natrugal cubic B-spline	10, 75, 90	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5, 50, 95 • 10, 50, 90 • 5, 75, 95
Cantering Value for Predictions Compares risk at different thresholds	75 th to 99 th percentile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 50th to 95th percentile • 75th to 99th percentile • 75th to 95th percentile
Heat Exposure	Mean 2m Air Temperature	2m Air Temperature, Wet Bulb Globe Temperature, Universal Thermal Climate Index, Heat Index <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimum • Mean • Maximum • Diurnal

4.2.2 Effect modification

We looked for evidence of effect modification, both from demographic (maternal age, sex of infant) and environmental factors (Koppen-Geiger Climate Zone, three hottest months of the year) (Table 3).

Table 3. Details of effect modifiers

Type of Effect Modifier	Effect Modifier	Levels	Details
Demographic	Maternal Age (years)	<25, 25-35, >35	Benin, Malawi, Tanzania, and Uganda did not have sufficient volumes for mothers above 35 years of age, and therefore were excluded for the >35 age group
	Infant Sex	Female, Male	Greece does not have infant sex, and so was excluded from the model
Sociodemographic	Continent	Africa Europe	
Environmental	Koppen-Geiger Climate Zone	A – Tropical B – Arid C – Temperate D – Continental E – Polar	
	Three Hottest Months	Three hottest consecutive months	

4.2.3 Software

All analyses were conducted in R version 4.4.1, using packages DLNM version 2.4.7 and mixmeta 1.2.0. Each country conducted its own analysis following standardised protocols, which included a unified script, codebook, and statistical plan. The resulting summary data and metadata were then submitted to the University of Witwatersrand in South Africa, who performed the evidence synthesis. All code, data dictionaries, and code instruction manual will be made freely available at time of publishing.

4.3 Time-to-event analysis

For the long-term heat exposure analysis, we applied a two-stage analytical approach.

In the first stage, country-specific associations between trimester-specific heat exposure and each birth outcome were estimated using Cox proportional hazards models, with 22 weeks as follow up time. Models were adjusted for relevant covariates, such as season of conception, year of birth, municipality code, maternal age, Body Mass Index, education, sex of infants. To characterise potential nonlinear relationship, natural cubic splines with 3 degrees of freedom were applied to each heat metric for each trimester. We estimated hazard ratios (HR) and 95% confidence intervals by comparing 99th percentile of temperature to 75th percentile (used as the reference). All analyses were harmonised via a common study protocol and shared code. Each country conducted its analyses locally, and results were centralised at Karolinska Institutet.

In the second stage, we performed a random-effects meta-analysis to pool the country-specific associations. To assess the heterogeneity across countries, we calculated the I^2 statistic and corresponding P-values using Cochran's Q test. All analyses were conducted using the statistical software R 4.0.3 (R Development Core Team).

5 Results

This chapter presents both comparative and country-specific findings:

- The short-term and long-term analyses present cross-country findings, allowing for comparative insights across the countries;
- Greece and Kenya are highlighted with individual country findings, due to the unique characteristics and structure of their datasets.

Data from other countries (e.g. Austria, Belgium, the LAC region) have just been analysed or are being analysed, and their findings will be included in the final cross-country analyses and related publications.

5.1 Short-term heat exposure

The analysis is still ongoing, and so the current results include eight countries: Benin, Malawi, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Greece, Italy and Sweden. In total, we included 4,161,855 singleton births (range: 23,835 Tanzania – 2,316,655 Greece), of which 362,387 (8.7 %) were preterm births (PTBs) (range: 5.0% Sweden – 17.1% South Africa), 20,429 (0.5%) were stillbirths (SB) (range: 0.1% Italy – 7.2% Benin) and 24,345 (0.6%) live-birth infants had a low APGAR score at 5 minutes (range: 0.5% Italy – 4.5% South Africa) (Table 4).

Table 4. Childbirth population characteristics of 8 locations (1999-2023)

Continent	Country	Time Period	Data collection Method	Total births	Preterm Birth n (%)	Stillbirth n (%)	Low APGAR n (%)
Africa	Benin	2021-2023	Hospital Birth Registry	26,438	4,432 (16.8)	1,893 (7.2)	1,182 (4.5)
	Malawi	2021-2023	Hospital Birth Registry	50,539	5,286 (10.5)	944 (1.9)	1,324 (2.6)
	South Africa	2017 - 2022	Sub-District Birth Registry	189,669	18,280 (17.1)*	2,394 (1.3)	8,575 (4.5)
	Tanzania	2021-2023	Hospital Birth Registry	23,837	3,197 (13.4)	369 (1.5)	290 (1.2)
	Uganda	2021-2023	Hospital Birth Registry	37,402	3,940 (10.5)	1,680 (4.5)	1,364 (3.6)
Europe	Greece	1999 - 2021	National Birth Registry	2,316,655	211,366 (9.1)	10,115 (0.4)	-

Continent	Country	Time Period	Data collection Method	Total births	Preterm Birth n (%)	Stillbirth n (%)	Low APGAR n (%)
	Italy	2001 - 2019	National Birth Registry	856,700	50,176 (5.9)	1,114 (0.1)	4,022 (0.5)
	Sweden	2014 - 2018	National Birth Registry	560,615	28,143 (5.0)	1,920 (0.3)	7,588 (1.4)

Note: Greece did not have APGAR score available. *PTB was restricted to the tertiary hospital (n=106,626) births as gestational age at clinic level was not reliable.

5.1.1 Main results

In meta-analysis, compared to the 75th percentile of mean temperature a week before birth, we found that the 99th percentile was associated with a 10% increase in the odds of PTB [OR=1.10; 95% CI:1.05 - 1.16; $I^2=1\%$] (Figure 7), with low heterogeneity. The point estimate was larger in Africa [OR=1.18; 95% CI:0.97 - 1.44] versus Europe [OR=1.09; 95% CI: 1.02 - 1.18], although the difference was not statistically significant (sub-group difference p-value: 0.28). The largest effect size was observed in Tanzania (OR=1.58 [95% CI: 1.09-2.28]), with only Greece and Tanzania demonstrating statistically significant associations.

Figure 7. Effects of mean temperature on the odds of preterm birth

Note: a) Meta-Analysis Results for Preterm Birth. b) Meta-analysis results for stillbirth. c) Forest plot for Low APGAR Score.

Compared to the 75th percentile of mean temperature, we found that the 99th percentile was associated with an 8% increase in the odds of SB [95% CI:0.96 - 1.22; I²=0%] (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Effects of mean temperature on the odds of stillbirth

The point estimate was larger in Africa [OR=1.19; 95% CI:0.95 - 1.50] versus Europe [OR=1.03; 95% CI:0.86 - 1.22], although the difference was not statistically significant (sub-group difference p-value: 0.28). The highest OR was observed in Malawi (OR=1.62 [95% CI: 0.82-3.22]), with no countries demonstrating statistically significant associations. We deemed meta-analysis inappropriate for low APGAR scores due to heterogeneity of results, with both increased and decreased associations observed across the countries (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Meta-analysis of low APGAR score

Note: Deemed inappropriate for inclusion based on protective and harmful effects observed, but presented for completeness

When looking at the relationship between different durations of exposure to heat in the last week of pregnancy and adverse birth outcomes, we observed an increase in the odds of PTB with each subsequent day of exposure to mean temperature in the 99th percentile, although the difference between sub-groups was not statistically significant, while consistent effects were observed for SB (Figure 10a).

Figure 10. Sensitivity analyses

Note: All lines represent meta-analysis estimates. a) Lags. Main model = lag 0-6. b) Models. Poly = polynomial, with 2 or 3 degrees of freedom. Ns = natural cubic spline with 3, 4 or 5 knots. Main model = natural cubic spline with 2 knots

Changing the model (polynomial versus cubic spline) produced consistent effects for both PTB and SB, as did altering the knot points (Figure 10b and c). When comparing different risk thresholds, we observed a statistically significant higher effect estimate for PTB when comparing the risk at the 50th percentile compared to the 95th percentile of mean temperature (OR=1.14 [95%CI: 1.09 – 1.20; $I^2=0\%$]), with no difference observed for SB (Figure 10d).

➤ Exposure-Response Curves

In meta-regression, we observed a threshold exposure-response curve for both PTB and SB, with no effect observed below the 75th percentile (about 20.3°C), followed by an increase in the odds of adverse events (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Exposure-response curves

Note: a) Preterm birth b) Stillbirth and c) Low APGAR score

PTB demonstrated the only statistically significant effect. We observed an inverted U-shaped exposure-response relationship for low APGAR score, although the effects were not statistically significant.

5.1.2 Heat exposure

We observed no statistically significant difference in effect estimates for PTB and SB between mean, minimum and maximum temperature, WBGT, UTCI or Heat Index (Figure 12).

Only mean temperature and UTCI, maximum WBGT and UTCI, and minimum temperature and Heat Index demonstrated statistically significant effects for PTB, while no exposure produced a statistically significant effect for SB. Diurnal range demonstrated inconsistent patterns of effect for PTB.

Figure 12. Meta-analysis estimates for different heat exposures

Note: Wet Bulb Globe Temperature does not include Benin, Malawi, Tanzania or Uganda due to limited availability of the exposure.

5.1.3 Effect modification

No statistically significant effect modification was observed by maternal age, infant sex, climate zone or time of year, although slightly stronger effects for PTB and SB were observed in younger (<25) and older (>35) mothers, female infants, in tropical climate zones for PTB, and temperate zones for SB, and in the three hottest months of the year (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Effect modification

Note: Effect modification by a) Maternal age (in years). Main model = all ages. >35 does not contain results from Benin, Malawi, Tanzania or Uganda due to small sample sizes. b) Infant sex. Main model = all infants. Male and female categories do not include Greece, as infant sex was not available. c) Koppen-Geiger Climate Zones. Main model = all climate zones. Climate zones were assigned within each country. d) Time of year. Main model = all 12 months.

5.2 Long-term heat exposure

In total, 4,924,422 mother-child pairs from Sweden, Belgium, Italy, and Greece were involved in the analysis. Table 5 shows the example of Sweden, including the mean air temperature, UTCI, WBGT, heat index throughout three trimesters. Temperature increased by approximately 5 to 10 °C from the 75th to the 99th percentile in each country.

In general, the correlation matrix of each country (Figure 14) showed that the correlation between the first and second trimester, between the second and third trimester were close to 0, while the correlation between the first and third trimester was close to -1. Different heat metrics were highly correlated to each other; most r values were close to 1.

Table 5. The mean, 50th, 75th, 99th percentile daily mean temperature, UTCI, WBGT, Heat Index through three trimesters in Sweden

	Mean of heat metrics (Celsius)	50th percentile of heat metrics (Celsius)	75th percentile of heat metrics (Celsius)	99th percentile of heat metrics (Celsius)
1st trimester	7.8/1.0/6.5/6.8	7.4/0.5/6.2/6.4	13.5/10.2/11.9/13.2	18.4/17.4/17.3/19.8
2nd trimester	7.4/0.5/6.2/6.4	7.0/-0.1/5.8/5.9	12.7/9.0/11.1/12.2	17.9/16.5/17.1/19.5
3rd trimester	7.9/0.3/6.6/6.9	7.7/1.3/6.4/6.7	13.6/10.4/12.0/13.3	18.4/17.3/22.1/23.3

Figure 14. Correlation matrix for different heat metrics by trimester of Sweden (A), Belgium (B), Italy (C), Greece (D)

Our pooled results from Sweden, Belgium, Italy, and Greece showed that the strongest associations were consistently observed in the third trimester for all outcomes. An increase in mean temperature from the 75th to the 99th percentile in the second and third trimesters was associated with higher risks of preterm birth (HR=1.04, 95%CI:1.02-1.07, $I^2=63.5\%$; HR=1.58, 95%CI:1.40-1.77, $I^2=99.4\%$). Sweden exhibited the strongest association for the third trimester among the four countries. As for stillbirth, we found that exposure during the third trimester was associated with a higher risk (HR=1.58, 95%CI:1.50-1.67, $I^2=6.3\%$), and the strongest association was found in Belgium. Increased temperature during the third trimester was associated with higher risks of SGA (HR=1.17, 95%CI:1.12-1.22, $I^2=94.6\%$) and LGA (HR=1.13, 95%CI:1.08-1.18, $I^2=93.9\%$), with strongest effects observed in Sweden (Figures 15-17).

The associations of mean UTCI, WBGT, and heat index assessed during the third trimester with birth outcomes were comparable to those observed for mean temperature. And the effect size of the third trimester was similar across different heat metrics. However, there were slightly different estimates across the heat metrics in other trimesters. For example, we found that exposure to increased temperature in the first trimester was associated with a higher risk of preterm birth, but no association was observed in the second trimester. In contrast, for UTCI, WBGT, and Heat Index, significant associations occurred in the second trimester but not in the first. Besides, increased temperature exposure in the first trimester was associated with a higher risk of stillbirth, while similar association was not found for other heat metrics. Increased air temperature, UTCI, and Heat Index in the first trimester were associated with a higher risk of SGA, whereas no association in the first trimester was observed for WBGT.

Figure 15. Forest plot depicting the meta-analysis examining the associations between trimester-specific heat indicators (temperature, UTCI, WBGT, heat index) and preterm birth across four countries in Europe (Sweden, Belgium, Italy, Greece)

Figure 16. Forest plot depicting the meta-analysis examining the associations between trimester-specific heat indicators (temperature, UTCI, WBGT, heat index) and stillbirth across four countries in Europe (Sweden, Belgium, Italy, Greece)

Figure 17. Forest plot depicting the meta-analysis examining the associations between trimester-specific heat indicators (temperature, UTCI, WBGT, heat index) and low birth weight across four countries in Europe (Sweden, Belgium, Italy, Greece)

Country-specific associations also presented similar pattern for different outcomes. Results from all the countries consistently showed associations for exposure to increased mean temperature from the 75th to the 99th percentile and PTB, SB, and LBW mainly in the third trimester and the associations exhibited a U-shaped curve. For the results from individual country, Greece showed the associations with PTB (HR=1.15, 95%CI: 1.13-1.17; HR=1.05, 95%CI: 1.03-1.07) and LBW (HR=1.15, 95%CI: 1.13-1.18; HR=1.05, 95%CI: 1.03-1.07) in the first and second trimester. Italy also presented the associations with PTB both in the first and second trimester (HR=1.08, 95%CI: 1.04-1.12; HR=1.07, 95%CI: 1.04-1.11), but no association with LBW in the first trimester (HR=1.03, 95%CI: 0.99-1.07). Sweden indicated the strongest associations in the third trimester on PTB (Sweden: HR=1.79, 95%CI: 1.70-1.88; Belgium: HR=1.56, 95%CI: 1.51-1.60; Italy: HR=1.65, 95%CI: 1.60-1.71; Greece: HR=1.35, 95%CI: 1.33-1.38) and LBW (Sweden: HR=1.73, 95%CI: 1.63-1.84; Belgium: R=1.48, 95%CI: 1.43-1.53; Italy: HR=1.52, 95%CI: 1.46-1.58; Greece: HR=1.26, 95%CI: 1.23-1.28) compared with other three countries. Except Belgium, other three countries consistently demonstrated that no associations were observed for SB in the first (Sweden: HR=1.09, 95%CI: 0.89-1.33; Italy: HR=1.04, 95%CI: 0.82-1.33; Greece: HR=1.06, 95%CI: 0.98-1.16) and second trimester (Sweden: HR=1.21, 95%CI: 1.00-1.46; Italy: HR=1.15, 95%CI: 0.92-1.43; Greece: HR=0.99, 95%CI: 0.91-1.07), however, significant associations were found in the third trimester (Sweden: HR=1.52, 95%CI: 1.23-1.87; Italy: HR=1.67, 95%CI: 1.24-2.09; Greece: HR=1.53, 95%CI: 1.40-1.68). In Belgium, significant associations were observed in the first and third trimesters with PTB (HR=1.04, 95%CI: 1.01-1.07; HR=1.56, 95%CI: 1.51-1.60), SB (HR=1.22, 95%CI: 1.08-1.38; HR=1.67, 95%CI: 1.44-1.94), and LBW (HR=1.05, 95%CI: 1.01-1.08; HR=1.48, 95%CI: 1.43-1.53). (Figures 18-20).

Figure 18. Hazard ratios (and 95% confidence intervals) of preterm birth associated with mean daily temperature during three trimesters of pregnancy in Sweden, Italy, Greece, and Belgium

Figure 19. Hazard ratios (and 95% confidence intervals) of SB associated with mean daily temperature during three trimesters of pregnancy in Sweden, Italy, Greece, and Belgium

Figure 20. Hazard ratios (and 95% confidence intervals) of low birth weight associated with mean daily temperature during three trimesters of pregnancy in Sweden, Italy, Greece, and Belgium

5.3 Individual country findings

In addition to the above cross-country analyses examining the short- and long-term effects of heat exposure on perinatal health outcomes, we conducted country-specific studies using data from Greece and Kenya, with further analyses planned for Austria.

The interest in Greece to explore additional environmental factors resulted in a comprehensive analysis of the adverse health effects of environmental exposure.

The Kenyan dataset was too small to be included in the above cross-country analyses, with about 650 births in the Aga Khan Hospital Mombasa hospital annually, for the period 2017-2022. Therefore a separate analysis using the hospital data was conducted.

5.3.1 Influence of environmental exposure in Greece

In the Greek dataset, individual analysis focused on several environmental indicators that included temperature, greenness (NDVI), and air pollutants (PM_{10} , $PM_{2.5}$, NO_2 , SO_2 , CO , O_3). Using time-to-event Cox proportional hazards models and data from over 2.3 million births (1999–2021), the study assessed outcomes including preterm birth, stillbirth, low birth weight, and small/large for gestational age.

Heat exposure in the third trimester was consistently linked to increased risks, particularly in urban and inland regions like Athens and Thessaloniki. Regional stratification (NUTS-3) highlighted spatial variability in risk, suggesting environmental and socio-demographic influences.

Higher third-trimester greenness was associated with modest protective effects across all outcomes. Women in the lowest 10th percentile of NDVI faced 3–5% increased hazard for PTB, LBW, SB, and abnormal foetal growth, while those in the highest 90th percentile saw equivalent risk reductions. Pollutant-specific findings indicated:

- **PM_{10} and $PM_{2.5}$:** Higher exposure increased risk of PTB, LBW, and SB; lower exposure was protective.
- **SO_2 :** High exposure raised risk for PTB and LBW; associations with SB and SGA were weak or null.
- **NO_2 :** Strongest pollutant effects observed,
- **CO :** Moderate increases in PTB and LBW risk at high exposure; low exposure offered some protection.

- **O₃**: Unique inverse pattern, where high exposure seemed protective, possibly due to confounding with other pollutants.

The study's strengths include its large sample size and harmonised national exposure assessment. Limitations include the use of modelled pollution data, spatial averaging, and single-pollutant modelling.

A detailed description of the results is provided in Annex.

5.3.2 Influence of heat exposure in Kenya

Using the data from the Aga Khan Hospital in Mombasa, Kenya, influence of heat metrics on the aforementioned perinatal health outcomes as well as on caesarean sections, assisted vaginal deliveries and long duration of stay in hospital (>5 days in hospital), was evaluated. The study relies on a pooled time series regression using distributed-lag nonlinear models (lag 0-9 months). The results are displayed as relative risk ratios (median value of exposure to the 95th percentile) of the rise in percentage of health outcomes observed in each month (i.e. number of babies born experiencing a health outcome in comparison to the total times by 100).

For caesarean sections an increased odds with heat exposure at lag 0 indicated by maximum daily Universal Thermal Climate Index between the median and the 95th percentile (relative risk 1.21 (1.01,1.46, 95%CI)) and maximum daily temperature (1.25 (1.03,1.53)) was observed. Similar increased odds of low birth weight births for lag 0 mean and maximum UTCI were found. Wet Bulb Globe Temperature showed no significant responses. Except caesarean section and low birth weight, no other outcomes showed significant results. In the publication "The influence of heat exposure on birth and neonatal outcomes in Mombasa, Kenya: a pooled time series analysis" provides a detailed description of the findings [31]. The reason for not including Kenya into the multi-country analysis lies in the small number of records. Compared to the nationwide total of 1.6 million births in 2024, this dataset is too small to draw reliable conclusions about the general population

[32]. Also, with just around 520 births per year on average, there is a factor 100 and higher difference to the other country datasets which are therefore much more indicative.

6 Discussion

6.1 Short-term heat exposure

Across two continents, eight countries and 4,161,855 singleton births, we found evidence of an association between exposure to high mean temperatures the week before birth and adverse neonatal and foetal outcomes, with stronger effects in Africa compared to Europe.

Consistent effects across countries and climate zones points to the relevance of PTB as a potential global indicator for the effects of heat on neonatal health. When mean temperature the week before birth increased from the 75th to the 99th percentile, we found an overall 10% increase in the odds of PTB. This was consistent with a systematic review of 39 studies comparing high versus low heat exposure less than 4 weeks before birth, which found a 12% increase in the odds of PTB [4]. Harmful effects were found across all countries, although only three reached statistical significance, with the largest effect observed in Tanzania (58%). We found evidence of a larger effect in Africa compared to Europe, with an 18% increase in African countries compared to 9% in European countries, although the difference did not reach statistical significance. This is consistent with an overall greater burden of PTB in Africa (15.9%) compared with Europe (10.9%) in our dataset, and in worldwide estimates [33]. The ability to adapt and prevent the effects of heat is more advanced in high-income countries, which we believe provides a plausible explanation for the difference in numbers.

Although not statistically significant, we found an 8% increase in the odds of SB with exposure to the 99th percentile of mean temperature the week before birth

compared to exposure to the 75th percentile, with 19% in Africa compared to 3% in Europe. This was consistent with the largest systematic review and meta-analysis of the effects of high heat exposure less than 4 weeks before birth which found a 13% increase in the odds of SB across nine studies [4].

We did not see consistent direction of effects in the estimates for the impact of high heat exposure on low APGAR scores, with both decreased (Malawi, Tanzania, Italy) and increased (Benin, South Africa, Uganda, Sweden) associations observed across countries, with only Malawi reaching statistical significance. Previous studies have found significant heterogeneity in the reliability and validity of APGAR score at capturing the clinical status of infants, which may have contributed to our inconsistent results [34]. Our results appear robust to sensitivity analyses, and with different heat indicators. Mean, maximum and minimum temperature, WBGT and UHCI showed consistent effects, while diurnal range showed inconsistent effect.

The strength of our work lies in the harmonised statistical approach, uniform exposure assessment, large geographical representation, and high quality of source data. We observed a decrease in the heterogeneity of our estimates, from 92% in the meta-analysis of 39 studies looking at PTB to 1% in our estimate, and 83% in a meta-analysis of 9 studies looking at SB to 0% in our estimate [4].

Despite the significant sample size and geographic coverage, significant limitations exist. First, the study includes a difference in the size and quality of data across the regions. While the data from European countries come from national birth registries maintained by civil registration and vital statistics agencies, the data from the African cohorts are obtained from hospital registries that were set up and maintained through research studies. Second, heat exposure was assigned differently in Europe and in Africa. In European countries, heat exposure was assigned according to the mothers residence, whereas in African countries it was assigned according to hospital of delivery due to limited availability of information

on the mother's location. Finally, we used exposure from ERA5 reanalysis data. Previous work has shown ERA5 to significantly underestimate extreme temperatures in certain geographical locations, potentially biasing our estimates downwards [35].

6.2 Long-term heat exposure

The long-term study explores the association between trimester-specific exposure of pregnant women to ambient temperatures and adverse birth outcomes. Four countries in Europe involving more than 4 million births were included. We found that exposure of pregnant women to ambient temperature in the third trimester was associated with an increased risk of adverse birth outcomes, including PTB, SB, and low birth weight. Different heat indicators such as daily temperature, UTCI, WBGT, Heat index present similar results.

The present analysis adds to the growing body of evidence indicating that maternal heat exposure, particularly during the third trimester, significantly increases the risk of adverse birth outcomes. A remarkable consistency is observed across the country-specific results, with all sub-cohorts showing a U-shaped exposure–response pattern for ambient temperature exposure during the third trimester of pregnancy. In general, the effects of the first and second trimester were milder and occasionally not statistically significant although some indications of adverse effects are recorded. While pooled analyses provide a robust overall picture, country-specific trends reveal additional insights. Sweden exhibited the highest risks in the third trimester for all outcomes, particularly PTB (HR=1.79) and LBW (HR=1.73), which may reflect a greater susceptibility due to generally cooler climates and lower baseline heat acclimatisation. Conversely, Greece and Belgium showed notable associations earlier in pregnancy, including in the first trimester, suggesting possible regional differences in vulnerability windows. Italy's patterns were more consistent with the pooled results, with

elevated PTB risks in the first and second trimesters and significant third-trimester associations for both PTB and SB.

Our findings align with global evidence showing the third trimester as the most vulnerable period for heat-related preterm birth. We observed the strongest associations during this period across all countries consistent with studies identifying late pregnancy (weeks 28 to 40 of gestation) as a key window for heat-induced labour triggers [36,37]. Additionally, significant second-trimester associations in Greece and Italy support literature suggesting a mid-pregnancy vulnerability [36], indicating both acute and delayed pathways to PTB.

Our findings also strongly support prior evidence identifying the third trimester, particularly the final weeks of pregnancy, as the most critical window for heat-related stillbirth. In our pooled analysis, significant associations were only observed in the third trimester across all countries, consistent with studies reporting elevated stillbirth risks from both acute (e.g., 7-day) and cumulative third-trimester heat exposure [38]. The literature suggests mechanisms including maternal dehydration, placental insufficiency, and foetal heat stress, which may explain the sharp increase in risk during sustained high temperatures late in gestation.

Concerning LBW, while some studies identify the first trimester as the most critical window for heat-related foetal growth restriction and low birth weight [39,40], our study found the strongest associations in the third trimester across all countries, although some country specific results are suggestive of a first and second trimester effect.

7 Conclusions

Both short term and longer term heat exposures studies across multiple countries have demonstrated increased risks of heat exposure on adverse birth outcomes.

These findings will help policy makers to draft public intervention strategies in order to reduce the burden of adverse birth outcomes caused by prenatal temperature exposure.

The data analyses of short-term and long-term heat exposure on maternal and newborn health outcomes revealed that:

- Heat exposure during pregnancy, especially in the final week and third trimester, is associated with adverse birth outcomes, such as preterm birth and stillbirth;
- Data from African countries show stronger associations than data from European countries, possibly due to higher baseline risks and data limitations;
- Results are consistent across different heat indicators (mean, max, min temperature, WBGT, UTCI), except for diurnal range.

By using several heat metrics and harmonised methodologies we enhanced the reliability of the findings.

Our analysis also shows that more effort is needed to improve health and socio-economic data availability to further study effect modification and potential for resilience and adaptation, and homogenise methodologies and health data collection across different countries and world regions, although we have made a step forward by implementing a uniform analysis approach. To date, we have included all the countries listed in our protocol in our analyses: Greece, Italy, Sweden, Kenya and South Africa. The geographical scope was expanded with the datasets from seven countries in Latin America and the Caribbean (Argentina, Bolivia, Ecuador, Guatemala, Honduras, the Dominican Republic and Uruguay), four in Africa (Benin, Malawi, Tanzania and Uganda) and two in Europe (Austria and Belgium). Although it was planned to include Kenya and Austria in the first round of analysis, small sample sizes and spatial resolution compatibility issues

made this not possible. This highlights remaining difficulties in the data collection and analysis process and indicates potential for improvement.

Further research is needed to clarify biological mechanisms and identify the most vulnerable periods during pregnancy. Within HIGH Horizons we plan to expand the health outcomes analysed so far. The initial round of data analysis focused on the above priority health outcomes, as these are the most commonly studied and consistently available across all our country datasets. However, only a limited number of cross-country studies using the same statistical methods are currently available. The second round of data analysis will be focused on maternal complications such as hypertensive disorders and gestational diabetes.

The HIGH Horizons project focuses, amongst other objectives, on the selection of global heat-health indicators for monitoring the impact of heat on MNCH, and the findings of this report will feed into the selection and prioritisation of these indicators by the Expert Group convened by WHO for this purpose, and into the forthcoming joint WHO-UNICEF-UNFPA-WMO publication, comprising global and national indicators to monitor the impacts of heat on MNCH.

8 Annex: Individual analysis of Greek data

The results reported in section 5.2 show that, in Greece, associations between third-trimester exposures and birth outcomes were the most consistent and largest in magnitude compared with other gestational periods. This section outlines the principal outputs of the third-trimester environmental exposure analysis which was based on the methodology described in section 4.3, i.e. the time-to-event analysis. We examined greenness (NDVI) and multiple air pollutants (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂, SO₂, O₃, CO) in relation to five perinatal outcomes: PTB, SB, low birth weight, and SGA/LGA. We applied the modelling framework (Cox proportional hazards with common covariate adjustment) for the heat-health

examination, after a regional NUTS-3 stratification used to assess spatial heterogeneity. Next, we assessed the effect of various environmental indicators at a nation-wide scale. The core sections present exposure–response figures annotated with percentile markers and confidence bands, alongside tables reporting hazard ratios for contrasts between low, median, and high exposure percentiles. Findings are planned to be published.

➤ **Regional Stratified Analysis of Third-Trimester Temperature and Birth Outcomes (NUTS-3 Level)**

We estimated region-specific associations between third-trimester temperature and birth outcomes by repeating the same analysis separately within each NUTS-3 region. First, the national data were split into regional subsets. For each region, we modelled time from 22 gestational weeks to the outcome, adjusting for key maternal and temporal factors (age group, season of conception, birth year) and accounting for local administrative strata. Temperature was treated as a continuous exposure, and we contrasted high versus moderate conditions using the 99th and 75th percentiles of each region’s own distribution to keep comparisons meaningful despite differing climates. From each model we extracted the hazard ratio and 95% confidence interval for this contrast and stored the results in a single table. These region-level estimates were then mapped to visualise spatial heterogeneity and highlight clusters of elevated or reduced risk.

The stratified results are shown in Figures GR1–GR3: GR1 (Preterm Birth), GR2 (Low Birth Weight), and GR3 (Stillbirth).

Figure GR1. Regional (NUTS-3) Hazard Ratios for Preterm Birth Associated with 3rd-Trimester Exposure (99th vs 75th Percentile)

Figure GR2. Regional (NUTS-3) Hazard Ratios for Low Birth Weight Associated with 3rd-Trimester Exposure (99th vs 75th Percentile)

Figure GR3. Regional (NUTS-3) Hazard Ratios for Stillbirth Associated with 3rd-Trimester Exposure (99th vs 75th Percentile)

Heat exposure in the third trimester is associated with adverse birth outcomes across most Greek regions. Clear spatial patterns did not emerge, yet several tendencies appear. Effects are relatively larger in regions containing major urban centres, notably Athens and Thessaloniki. Central Greece also shows higher estimates, consistent with warmer inland conditions. Coastal and island regions often display weaker or null associations, possibly due to moderating maritime climates or differing population characteristics, although this pattern is not consistent in all island regions. Residual confounding, exposure misclassification, and limited regional sample sizes may contribute to the observed heterogeneity. Overall, the findings indicate widespread heat-related risk, with suggestive hotspots in highly urbanised and warmer inland areas.

➤ Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and birth outcomes

The Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is a satellite-derived measure of greenness commonly used as an indicator of residential exposure to green space. There is a growing interest on the relationship between greenness and

birth outcomes in the recent literature. Two meta-analyses confirm that residential greenness (NDVI) modestly improves birth outcomes, especially birth weight. Hu et al. (2021) pooled 29 studies, finding each NDVI increment linked to 8–15 g higher birth weight and 7–21% lower low birth weight odds (ORs 0.79–0.93), with no effect on PTB or SGA [41]. Zhan et al. (2020) showed a linear dose–response trend between NDVI and reduced low birth weight risk, though PTB findings were inconsistent [42]. Large post-2020 studies reinforce greenness’s weight benefits, but PTB associations remain unclear.

In this analysis we evaluated mean NDVI values during the 3rd trimester of pregnancy in relation to several adverse birth outcomes using time-to-event (Cox proportional-hazards) models as described in section 4.3. NDVI exposure was treated continuously and we used a linear function to model the exposure–response, including NDVI and key covariates (maternal age category, conception season, birth year, urbanicity). From the fitted model, we derived hazard ratios and 95% confidence intervals across the observed NDVI range. We calculated HRs at the 10th and 90th percentiles versus the median and generated exposure–response curves, highlighting linear models’ point estimates and confidence bands.

The results are shown in Figure GR4 and Table GR1.

Figure GR4. Exposure–Response Curve for Trimester 3 NDVI Levels vs. various outcomes (Linear Models)

Table GR1: Hazard Ratios for the 10th and 90th Percentiles of Trimester 3 NDVI (Linear Models) across Birth Outcomes

Comparison	NDVI (T3)	Hazard Ratio	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
Preterm Birth				
10th vs 50th	0.140	1.041	1.034	1.048
90th vs 50th	0.563	0.965	0.960	0.971
Low Birth Weight				
10th vs 50th	0.140	1.051	1.044	1.059
90th vs 50th	0.563	0.957	0.951	0.963
Stillbirth				
10th vs 50th	0.140	1.038	1.002	1.076
90th vs 50th	0.563	0.967	0.938	0.998
Small for Gestational Age				
10th vs 50th	0.140	1.045	1.039	1.051
90th vs 50th	0.563	0.962	0.957	0.967
Large for Gestational Age				
10th vs 50th	0.140	1.030	1.024	1.036
90th vs 50th	0.563	0.974	0.969	0.980

Note: **a.** Models fitted via Cox proportional-hazards with a linear Trimester 3 NDVI term **b.** All models adjusted for maternal age, conception season, year of birth, and urbanicity. **c.** Outcomes defined as: Preterm birth (<37 weeks), SB (foetal death ≥22 weeks), SGA/LGA (<10th/ >90th birthweight percentile), LBW (<2,500 g).

Findings summary: Lower trimester 3 greenness was consistently associated with small but meaningful increases in risk across all outcomes, while higher greenness conferred modest protection. Specifically, women in the lowest 10th percentile of NDVI faced approximately 3–5% greater hazards of PTB, low birth weight, SB, and abnormal birthweight for gestational age compared to those at the median. In contrast, those in the highest 90th percentile experienced a similar magnitude of risk reduction. These patterns persisted after adjusting for maternal age, season of conception, birth year, and urbanicity.

➤ **Coarse particulate matter (PM₁₀) and birth outcomes**

Coarse particulate matter (PM₁₀) is linked to reduced birth weight and higher rates of low-birth-weight infants. A meta-analysis reported a 10% increase in the odds of LBW per 20 µg/m³ rise in PM₁₀ across pregnancy [43]. Exposure to PM₁₀ also modestly elevates PTB risk, with pooled third-trimester estimates showing a 6% higher odds per 20 µg/m³ increase [43].

In this analysis we evaluated mean PM10 values during the 3rd trimester of pregnancy in relation to several adverse birth outcomes using time-to-event (Cox proportional-hazards) models. The results are shown in Figure GR5 and Table GR2.

Figure GR5. Exposure–Response Curve for Trimester 3 PM10 Levels vs. various outcomes (Linear Models)

Table GR2. Hazard Ratios for the 10th and 90th Percentiles of Trimester 3 PM10 (Linear Models) across birth outcomes

Comparison	PM10(T3) [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Hazard Ratio	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
Preterm Birth				
10th vs 50th	13.705	0.939	0.930	0.948
90th vs 50th	26.140	1.065	1.055	1.075
Low Birth Weight				
10th vs 50th	13.705	0.970	0.960	0.980
90th vs 50th	26.140	1.031	1.020	1.042
Stillbirth				
10th vs 50th	13.705	0.917	0.866	0.970
90th vs 50th	26.140	1.090	1.031	1.153
Small for Gestational Age				
10th vs 50th	13.705	0.984	0.975	0.993
90th vs 50th	26.140	1.016	1.007	1.026
Large for Gestational Age				
10th vs 50th	13.705	0.957	0.947	0.967
90th vs 50th	26.140	1.045	1.034	1.055

Note: **a.** Models fitted via Cox proportional-hazards with a linear Trimester 3 NDVI term. **b.** All models adjusted for maternal age, conception season, year of birth, and urbanicity. **c.** Outcomes defined as: Preterm birth (<37 weeks), SB (foetal death ≥ 22 weeks), SGA/LGA (<10th/ >90th birthweight percentile), LBW (<2,500 g).

Findings summary: Across all outcomes, lower third-trimester PM₁₀ exposures were modestly protective, whereas higher exposures markedly increased risk. Compared with the median, women at the 10th percentile of PM₁₀ had 6–8% lower hazards of PTB, low birth weight, SB, and large- or small-for-gestational-age. Conversely, those at the 90th percentile faced 3–9% higher hazards: the greatest increase was seen for SB (≈9% higher) and PTB (≈6.5% higher).

➤ **Fine particulate matter PM_{2.5} and birth outcomes**

PM_{2.5} (fine particulate matter) refers to airborne particles with aerodynamic diameters ≤ 2.5 micrometers. Because of their small size, these particles can penetrate deep into the lungs and even enter the bloodstream.

Many studies show consistent associations between PM_{2.5} exposure and increased odds of low-birth-weight infants [44]. Exposure to fine particles is also linked to a higher chance of PTB [45]. Though studied less, PM_{2.5} has also been implicated in SB risk. One analysis noted that an increase in PM_{2.5} was associated with a higher chance of SB [45].

In this analysis we evaluated mean PM_{2.5} values during the 3rd trimester of pregnancy in relation to several adverse birth outcomes using time-to-event (Cox proportional-hazards) models as described above.

The results are shown in Figure GR6 and Table GR3.

Figure GR6. Exposure–Response Curve for Trimester 3 PM2.5 Levels vs. various outcomes (Linear Models)

Table GR3. Hazard Ratios for the 10th and 90th Percentiles of Trimester 3 PM2.5 (Linear Models) across Birth Outcomes

Comparison	PM10(T3)[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Hazard Ratio	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
Preterm Birth				
10th vs 50th	8.954	0.976	0.967	0.985
90th vs 50th	16.348	1.026	1.016	1.036
Low Birth Weight				
10th vs 50th	8.954	0.985	0.975	0.996
90th vs 50th	16.348	1.016	1.004	1.027
Stillbirth				
10th vs 50th	8.954	0.942	0.890	0.998
90th vs 50th	16.348	1.065	1.002	1.131
Small for Gestational Age				
10th vs 50th	8.954	1.003	0.994	1.012
90th vs 50th	16.348	0.997	0.987	1.007
Large for Gestational Age				
10th vs 50th	8.954	0.993	0.983	1.003
90th vs 50th	16.348	1.007	0.996	1.018

Note: **a.** Models fitted via Cox proportional-hazards with a linear Trimester 3 PM2.5 term. **b.** All models adjusted for maternal age, conception season, year of birth, and urbanicity. **c.** Outcomes defined as: Preterm birth (<37 weeks), SB (foetal death ≥ 22 weeks), SGA/LGA (<10th/ >90th birthweight percentile), LBW (<2,500 g).

Findings summary: Lower third-trimester PM_{2.5} (10th vs. 50th percentile) was associated with marginally reduced hazards of PTB, low birth weight and SB, with no clear effect on small- or large-for-gestational-age. Conversely, higher PM_{2.5} (90th vs. 50th percentile) increased risks of PTB, low birth weight, and SB while associations with SGA and LGA remained essentially null.

➤ **Sulphur dioxide (SO₂) and birth outcomes**

SO₂ (sulphur dioxide) is a gaseous air pollutant formed primarily by the oxidation of sulphur in fuels. Recent evidence indicates that higher prenatal SO₂ exposure modestly raises the risk of small-for-gestational-age or term low-birth-weight infants [46]. However, larger reviews and meta-analyses report inconsistent or non-significant associations between SO₂ and PTB or SB, suggesting its effects beyond foetal growth are weaker or less certain [47].

In this analysis we evaluated mean SO₂ values during the 3rd trimester of pregnancy in relation to several adverse birth outcomes using time-to-event (Cox proportional-hazards) models as described above.

The results are shown in Figure GR7 and Table GR4.

Figure GR7. Exposure-Response Curve for Trimester 3 SO₂ Levels vs. various outcomes (Linear Models)

Note: **a.** Solid green line shows the estimated hazard ratio (HR) for SB per unit increase in NDVI, relative to the cohort median. **b.** Shaded band is the 95% confidence interval (CI) around the HR estimate. **c.** Vertical red dotted lines mark the 10th, 50th (reference), and 90th percentiles of Trimester 3 SO₂. **d.** Models adjusted for maternal age category, conception season, year of birth, and urbanicity.

Table GR4. Hazard Ratios for the 10th and 90th Percentiles of Trimester 3 SO₂ (Linear Models) across Birth Outcomes

Comparison	SO ₂ (T3)[µg/m ³]	Hazard Ratio	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
<i>Preterm Birth</i>				
10th vs 50th	1.121	0.965	0.958	0.973
90th vs 50th	6.755	1.073	1.056	1.090
<i>Low Birth Weight</i>				
10th vs 50th	1.121	0.986	0.977	0.995
90th vs 50th	6.755	1.029	1.011	1.047
<i>Stillbirth</i>				
10th vs 50th	1.121	1.010	0.962	1.061
90th vs 50th	6.755	0.980	0.889	1.082
<i>Small for Gestational Age</i>				
10th vs 50th	1.121	1.001	0.993	1.009
90th vs 50th	6.755	0.998	0.982	1.014
<i>Large for Gestational Age</i>				
10th vs 50th	1.121	0.972	0.964	0.981
90th vs 50th	6.755	1.058	1.040	1.076

Note: **a.** Models fitted via Cox proportional-hazards with a linear Trimester 3 SO₂ term. **b.** All models adjusted for maternal age, conception season, year of birth, and urbanicity. **c.** Outcomes defined as: Preterm birth (<37 weeks), SB (foetal death ≥22 weeks), SGA/LGA (<10th/ >90th birthweight percentile), LBW (<2,500 g).

Findings summary: Lower third-trimester SO₂ exposures were modestly protective against PTB and low birth weight, whereas higher exposures increased risk. In contrast, those at the 90th percentile had 7–8% higher hazards for PTB and ~3% higher for low birth weight. Associations with SB and SGA were essentially null, while LGA risk rose by about 6% at high SO₂ levels.

➤ **Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂) and birth outcomes**

NO₂ is a marker of traffic pollution (emitted by vehicle engines and power plants). NO₂ exposure is associated with lower birth weights, with a meta-analysis reporting a 13.6 g decrease in birth weight per 10 µg/m³ increase [48]. It also correlates with moderately higher PTB risk, around a 7% increase per 10 µg/m³, though not all findings reach statistical significance [49]. In this analysis we evaluated mean nO2 values during the 3rd trimester of pregnancy in relation to several adverse birth outcomes using time-to-event (Cox proportional-hazards) models as described above. The results are shown in Figure GR8 and Table GR5.

Figure GR8. Exposure–Response Curve for Trimester 3 NO₂ Levels vs. various outcomes (Linear Models)

Note: **a.** Solid green line shows the estimated hazard ratio (HR) for SB per unit increase in NO₂ relative to the cohort median. **b.** Shaded band is the 95% confidence interval (CI) around the HR estimate. **c.** Vertical red dotted lines mark the 10th, 50th (reference), and 90th percentiles of Trimester 3 NO₂. **d.** Models adjusted for maternal age category, conception season, year of birth, and urbanicity.

Table GR5. Hazard Ratios for the 10th and 90th Percentiles of Trimester 3 NO₂ (Linear Models) across Birth Outcomes

Comparison	NO ₂ (T3)[µg/m ³]	Hazard Ratio	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
<i>Preterm Birth</i>				
10th vs 50th	1.726	0.972	0.969	0.975
90th vs 50th	23.509	1.164	1.146	1.182
<i>Low Birth Weight</i>				
10th vs 50th	1.726	0.985	0.982	0.989
90th vs 50th	23.509	1.080	1.061	1.099
<i>Stillbirth</i>				
10th vs 50th	1.726	0.992	0.974	1.011
90th vs 50th	23.509	1.041	0.946	1.146
<i>Small for Gestational Age</i>				
10th vs 50th	1.726	0.994	0.991	0.997
90th vs 50th	23.509	1.033	1.018	1.049
<i>Large for Gestational Age</i>				
10th vs 50th	1.726	0.981	0.978	0.984
90th vs 50th	23.509	1.108	1.089	1.127
<p>Note: a. Models fitted via Cox proportional-hazards with a linear Trimester 3 SO₂ term. b. All models adjusted for maternal age, conception season, year of birth, and urbanicity. c. Outcomes defined as: Preterm birth (<37 weeks), SB (foetal death ≥22 weeks), SGA/LGA (<10th/ >90th birthweight percentile), LBW (<2,500 g).</p>				

Findings summary: Lower third-trimester NO₂ exposures were modestly protective against most outcomes, whereas high exposures substantially increased risk. Pregnancies at the 10th percentile of NO₂ saw slight reductions in hazards for PTB, low birth weight, SGA, and LGA compared to the median. Conversely, those at the 90th percentile experienced the greatest risk elevation for PTB (~16% higher) and large-for-gestational-age (~11% higher), with moderate increases for low birth weight and SGA. SB showed no clear association. All models controlled for maternal age, season of conception, birth year, and urbanicity, indicating a graded exposure–response with NO₂.

➤ Carbon Monoxide (CO) and birth outcomes

Maternal CO exposure is consistently linked to lower birth weight, with a pooled estimate showing an average decrease of about 11.4 g per 1 ppm increase in CO over pregnancy [50]. Elevated CO levels are also modestly associated with higher

odds of PTB, though fewer studies address this and results are less consistent [50]. While its impacts are smaller than those of fine particulates, CO remains a significant traffic-related pollutant that negatively influences foetal growth and gestational duration.

In this analysis we evaluated mean CO values during the 3rd trimester of pregnancy in relation to several adverse birth outcomes using time-to-event (Cox proportional-hazards) models as described above.

The results are shown in Figure GR9 and Table GR6.

Figure GR9. Exposure–Response Curve for Trimester 3 CO Levels vs. various outcomes (Linear Models)

Note: **a.** Solid green line shows the estimated hazard ratio (HR) for SB per unit increase in CO relative to the cohort median. **b.** Shaded band is the 95% confidence interval (CI) around the HR estimate. **c.** Vertical red dotted lines mark the 10th, 50th (reference), and 90th percentiles of Trimester 3 CO. **d.** Models adjusted for maternal age category, conception season, year of birth, and urbanicity.

Table GR6. Hazard Ratios for the 10th and 90th Percentiles of Trimester 3 CO (Linear Models) across Birth Outcomes

Comparison	CO(T3)[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Hazard Ratio	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
<i>Preterm Birth</i>				
10th vs 50th	131.235	0.955	0.945	0.965
90th vs 50th	293.129	1.084	1.065	1.104
<i>Low Birth Weight</i>				
10th vs 50th	131.235	0.981	0.970	0.992
90th vs 50th	293.129	1.034	1.013	1.054
<i>Stillbirth</i>				
10th vs 50th	131.235	1.013	0.952	1.077
90th vs 50th	293.129	0.978	0.877	1.090
<i>Small for Gestational Age</i>				
10th vs 50th	131.235	0.999	0.989	1.009
90th vs 50th	293.129	1.002	0.985	1.020
<i>Large for Gestational Age</i>				
10th vs 50th	131.235	0.970	0.960	0.981
90th vs 50th	293.129	1.055	1.035	1.075
<p>Note: a. Models fitted via Cox proportional-hazards with a linear Trimester 3 SO₂ term. b. All models adjusted for maternal age, conception season, year of birth, and urbanicity. c. Outcomes defined as: Preterm birth (<37 weeks), SB (foetal death ≥ 22 weeks), SGA/LGA (<10th/ >90th birthweight percentile), LBW (<2,500 g).</p>				

Findings summary: Lower third-trimester CO exposures were modestly protective for PTB and low birth weight but had little effect on SB or SGA, whereas higher exposures significantly increased risk. Specifically, women at the 10th percentile of CO faced about 4–5% lower hazards for PTB (HR 0.955) and LBW (HR 0.981) relative to the median, while those at the 90th percentile experienced 8% higher preterm-birth risk (HR 1.084) and 3–6% higher risks for LBW (HR 1.034) and LGA (HR 1.055).

➤ Ozone (O₃) and birth outcomes

Ozone is a reactive gas formed in the atmosphere. Studies report weaker and less consistent ozone effects on PTB and low birth weight, and while a few studies suggest that short-term ozone spikes may trigger SB, the overall evidence for SB risk remains sparse and inconclusive [51]. In this analysis we evaluated mean O₃ values during the 3rd trimester of pregnancy in relation to several adverse birth

outcomes using time-to-event (Cox proportional-hazards) models as described above. The results are shown in Figure GR10 and Table GR7.

Figure GR10. Exposure–Response Curve for Trimester 3 O₃ Levels vs. various outcomes (Linear Models)

Table GR7. Hazard Ratios for the 10th and 90th Percentiles of Trimester 3 O₃ (Linear Models) across Birth Outcomes

Comparison	CO ₂ (T3)[µg/m ³]	Hazard Ratio	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
Preterm Birth				
10th vs 50th	48.546	1.028	1.011	1.046
90th vs 50th	91.110	0.980	0.969	0.992
Low Birth Weight				
10th vs 50th	48.546	1.042	1.023	1.062
90th vs 50th	91.110	0.971	0.958	0.984
Stillbirth				
10th vs 50th	48.546	0.972	0.879	1.076
90th vs 50th	91.110	1.020	0.949	1.097
Small for Gestational Age				
10th vs 50th	48.546	1.003	0.986	1.019
90th vs 50th	91.110	0.998	0.987	1.010
Large for Gestational Age				
10th vs 50th	48.546	1.008	0.990	1.027
90th vs 50th	91.110	0.994	0.981	1.007

Note: **a.** Models fitted via Cox proportional-hazards with a linear Trimester 3 SO₂ term. **b.** All models adjusted for maternal age, conception season, year of birth, and urbanicity. **c.** Outcomes defined as: Preterm birth (<37 weeks), SB (foetal death ≥22 weeks), SGA/LGA (<10th/ >90th birthweight percentile), LBW (<2,500 g).

Findings summary: In contrast to other pollutants, lower exposures (10th vs. 50th percentile) modestly increased hazards of PTB (HR 1.028, 95% CI 1.011–1.046) and low birth weight (HR 1.042, 1.023–1.062), whereas higher exposures (90th vs. 50th percentile) were slightly protective. O₃ often peaks under sunny, stagnant conditions when traffic-related pollutants like NO₂ and PM are lower, so it's apparent “protective” effect at high levels may simply reflect lower exposure to more harmful co-pollutants. This negative correlation can introduce confounding. Associations with SB, SGA, and LGA hovered around the null at both extremes.

➤ **Strengths, Limitations and Considerations**

This study utilises a very large, nation-wide dataset, providing high statistical power to detect modest effects and compare multiple outcomes. Harmonised exposure assignments for several pollutants and NDVI enable cross-pollutant contrasts within a consistent analytic framework. Common covariate adjustment (maternal age, season, birth year, urbanicity) enhances internal validity, and regional (NUTS-3) stratification reveals spatial heterogeneity that can inform targeted interventions. However, there are several important limitations to consider when interpreting our findings. First, we relied on Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service reanalysis data, which are model-based estimates of atmospheric pollutant concentrations, rather than ground-level monitoring. This can introduce measurement error, especially where topography or urban canyon effects cause local deviations from the grid averages. Second, exposures were assigned at the commune level, so everyone in the same administrative area received the same trimester-averaged value. This spatial aggregation masks within-commune variability, such as higher traffic-related pollution along major roads. Third, using fixed three-month blocks for trimester exposures may obscure shorter-term peaks (for example, wildfires or heatwaves). Fourth, because we used single-pollutant linear models, we could not disentangle the effects of

correlated pollutants, so some observed associations may reflect residual confounding by unmeasured co-pollutants. These factors suggest caution in causal interpretation and point to the value of higher-resolution exposure data, multi-pollutant modelling, and richer confounder information in future work.

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